

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ICONIZED EXEMPLAR IN MUSIC, ARTS,
PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND HEALTH (MAPEH)**

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Abstract

Introduction: Teachers are encouraged to deliver lessons in a way that is learner-centered, inclusive, and research-based through interdisciplinary and contextual approaches as part of the K–12 Curriculum's introduction of a culturally responsive and culture-sensitive, integrative, and contextualized, relevant, and responsive curriculum.

Methods: The interdisciplinary contextualized method links concepts and abilities within learning domains. The Department of Education (DepEd) uses interdisciplinary contextualization (Icon) in Science, Mathematics, and English, but MAPEH has never been researched. This research develops and validates iconized exemplars in music, arts, physical education, and health and examines their ramifications. The descriptive research design used the questionnaire to collect data. Forty-four heads, supervisor and expert teachers were the first group of respondents, and one hundred fifty grade 9 high school students were the second group of participants. The bulk of teacher respondents were from the DepEd Division of Nueva, especially District of Talavera, whereas all student respondents were from Talavera National High School.

Results: Results showed that practically all supervisors, department heads, and expert teachers characterized the four criteria of the iconized example in MAPEH—objectives, content, activities, and language—as "highly agree." Results also indicated that the supervisor and department heads' descriptions of MAPEH's iconized exemplar's aims differed from the expert teachers with a F value of 4.265 and p value of .045. Supervisors and department leaders score higher. Additionally, student conduct varied by sector. MAPEH students from various sections had distinct behavioral evaluations of iconized exemplars with F value of 5.636 and p value of .004.

Conclusions: The interdisciplinary contextualization of the four components of MAPEH—music, arts, physical education, and health—provides tailor-fit courses that accommodate and respect cultural, linguistic, and ethnic diversity, stimulates students to study MAPEH, and allows them to learn creatively.

Keywords: MAPEH, Development and Validation, Public School Teachers, K-12 Curriculum, Quality Education

Introduction

MAPEH stands for "music/arts/physical/health," and it is often considered by educators of all levels to be one of the most challenging subjects to teach. In addition to its four parts, the course places an emphasis on the student's intellectual, physical, and emotional growth. To teach MAPEH, educators need to have a firm grasp on four distinct but interrelated areas. Together, they help the learner develop a well-rounded set of skills and a more fertile imagination.

Teachers must find latent skills and utilize these creative features to develop future artists from these students. As a result, these instructors must fulfill a variety of duties to bring out the best in their pupils. Given the issues in the Philippine educational system today, such a project is formidable. These are evident in the findings of studies undertaken to analyze the influence of pre-service education among music, arts, physical education, and health majors, as well as teacher teaching styles and curriculum, on the learning outcomes of students in the aforementioned areas.

The problem goes beyond the inadequacy of teachers to teach the subject or simply attributing it to their professors for their lack of training during their undergraduate years (Bubka & Poberezhna, 2020). Some or majority of Filipino MAPEH teachers lack the necessary approach in teaching the very basic knowledge and skills of the subject. This may be since some teachers are non-MAPEH major graduates or lack training and seminars attended. This makes the MAPEH teachers feel inadequate in handling the subject. This adds to student related problems that include low level of interest and poor study habits.

One trait of a competent teacher is that the teacher must consistently strive to improve and develop their repertoire of teaching methodologies. The traditional way of teaching is found to be ineffective in reaching out to these "tech savvy" learners and these new breed of students aptly called "millennials" or "gen z's" need inventive and innovative strategies of imparting knowledge. This means instilling current instructional methodologies that form a transition from direct to indirect teaching (Castro, 2018).

On one end, there is direct instruction which is teacher-centered. Teacher-centered instruction believes that learning is a result of direct transmission of knowledge from teacher to student. On the other hand, indirect instruction is student-centered (Dauz & Ramos, 2019). Student-centered instruction believes that learning is a result of a student's ability to understand and process information. In the transition from direct (teacher-centered) to indirect (student-centered) the teacher is required to be competent and effectively create an environment conducive for learning.

Learning occurs only when the students (learners) process new information or knowledge in such a way that it makes sense to them in their own frames of reference (their own inner worlds of memory, experience, and response). This means focusing on the multiple aspects of any learning environment, whether classroom, laboratory, computer laboratory, worksite, or field. With the introduction of the K to 12 Curriculum which features a culturally responsive and culture sensitive, integrative, and contextualized, relevant, and responsive curriculum, teachers are now encouraged to deliver their lessons in a learner-centered, inclusive and research based through contextualized and localized approach. This means developing an enhanced basic curriculum that is contextualized and global but local in context. Thus, the interdisciplinary contextualized approach was introduced. The interdisciplinary contextualized approach is connecting/linking concept/skills within learning areas. This has been applied by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the areas of science, math and language and have shown promise and positive results (De Guzman et al., 2019).

However, as of present, use of interdisciplinary contextualization or "ICon" in MAPEH has never been explored or studied. Teachers rely on strategies traditionally used when teaching the components in MAPEH. Such traditional strategies like use of creative expression method, Kodaly method, simulation sight reading or technology related methods for music or simulation-part-whole, learning together and importance for physical education seems inadequate and further

widen the gap between the students learning and not learning by failing to stimulate their interest and engage learners in purposeful activities (Espiritu (2019).

The interdisciplinary contextualized approach to teaching MAPEH on the other hand answers the requirements of the 21st century learner as embodied in the demands of the K to 12 curriculum. As there is therefore a need to improve the teaching methodologies and competencies of MAPEH teachers so must the teachers themselves learn to able to interact better with their students (Guerrero & Daroy, 2019). The researcher, as a MAPEH teacher, believes that such commitment and advocacy for strategies that would improve learner retention, arouse interest, and promote creativity should be keenly observed and explored. Strategies wherein all techniques by which the teacher structure the learning environment, modify the tools and enhance the delivery of the lessons in a creative and constructive way so that the students are led to find out what they are supposed to discover. Hence, the researcher believes in the merit and the conduct of this study.

Research Questions

This study validated the developed iconized exemplar in Music, Arts, Physical Education and Health. Specifically, this seeks to answer the following questions: (1) How may the teacher-respondents describe the contents of the iconized exemplar in MAPEH in terms of: objective, content, activities, and language? (2) How may the iconized exemplar in MAPEH be described by the students? (3) What comments and suggestions did the student – respondents provide as they participated in the iconized exemplar in MAPEH? (4) Is there a significant difference on the description in the contents of the iconized exemplar in MAPEH among the EPS, heads, and expert teachers? (5) Is there a significant difference on the student’s behavior across age and section?

Methodology

Research Design. This study creates and verifies visual representations of exemplary activities in music, arts, physical education, and health and analyzes their effects. The study employed a descriptive research design and collected data using a survey questionnaire.

Sampling. Forty-four heads, supervisor and expert teachers were the first group of respondents, and one hundred fifty grade 9 high school students were the second group of participants. The bulk of teacher respondents were from the DepEd Division of Nueva, especially District of Talavera, whereas all student respondents were from Talavera National High School.

Instrumentations. Questionnaires were used to gather data from the respondents which were validated, and pilot tested. Validity score was 4.78 and Reliability index was .93 which is highly valid and very reliable respectively.

Data Analysis. Statistical tools such as frequency and percentage, mean, and analysis of variances (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data.

Results

The presented results cover various aspects of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program, including its description by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads (Table 1), comments and suggestions by students (not specified which group) on the program, significant difference on the description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH among EPS, Heads and Expert Teachers (Table 10), and significant difference on student’s description across age and section (Table 11).

Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads. Table 1 presents the mean results of the description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads, using four different indicators: Objectives, Content, Activities, and Language.

Table 1. Mean Results of the Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Objectives by Expert Teachers	4.82	Very Satisfactory
Objectives by Heads and EPS	4.52	Very Satisfactory
Content by Expert Teachers	4.52	Very Satisfactory
Content by Heads and EPS	4.58	Very Satisfactory
Activities by Expert Teachers	4.55	Very Satisfactory
Activities by Heads and EPS	4.66	Very Satisfactory
Language by Experts	4.57	Very Satisfactory
Language by Heads and EPS	4.64	Very Satisfactory
Composite Mean	4.61	Very Satisfactory

Legend:

1.00-1.79 – Very Unsatisfactory.

1.80-2.59 – Unsatisfactory

2.60-3.39 – Undecided

3.40-4.19 – Satisfactory

4.20 -5.00 – Very Satisfactory

The table also includes a Composite Mean, which is an average of all the indicators. The table presents the means for each indicator, along with a verbal interpretation based on a scale ranging from 1 to 5. The scale is labeled with verbal descriptors ranging from "Very Unsatisfactory" to "Very Satisfactory." The results suggest that both Expert Teachers and Heads and EPS rated the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH very satisfactorily, with mean scores ranging from 4.52 to 4.82 for the different indicators. The Composite Mean score of 4.61 also indicates a very satisfactory rating overall.

It is important to note that while the mean scores provide an indication of the overall level of satisfaction with the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH, they do not provide information about the variability or spread of the scores. Additionally, the scale used to interpret the mean scores is somewhat subjective and may vary depending on the context and the specific interpretation of the verbal descriptors used. Overall, Table 1 provides a general overview of the mean ratings of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads, suggesting high levels of satisfaction across different indicators.

Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH as Described by Students. Table 2 presents the mean rating of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program as described by students, using a single indicator. The table includes the Mean score and a verbal interpretation based on a scale ranging from 1 to 5. The scale is labeled with verbal descriptors ranging from "Very Unsatisfactory" to "Very Satisfactory."

Table 2. Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH as Described by Students

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Description of Iconized Exemplar by the Students	3.72	Satisfactory

Legend:

- 1.00-1.79 – Very Unsatisfactory.
- 1.80-2.59 – Unsatisfactory
- 2.60-3.39 – Undecided
- 3.40-4.19 – Satisfactory
- 4.20 -5.00 – Very Satisfactory

The results indicate that the mean rating of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program as described by students is 3.72, which falls under the category of "Satisfactory" according to the verbal interpretation. This suggests that students perceive the program to be moderately satisfactory in meeting their educational needs in the areas of Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health.

Comments and Suggestions by Students on the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH. The students who responded provided varying opinions about their acceptance and suggestions for the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program. However, overall, most of the students had a positive response to the program. Many of the student participants described the program as enjoyable and fun and used words such as exciting and understandable. They also stated that the program helped them to better comprehend the subject matter.

Significant Difference in the Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH among EPS, Heads and Expert Teachers. The table displays the results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) for four different variables (objectives, content, activities, and language) in relation to the description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) among three groups: EPS (Education Program Supervisor), Heads, and Expert Teachers. For each variable, the table shows the Sum of Squares, the degrees of freedom (df), the Mean Square, the F-statistic, and the significance level (Sig.).

Table 3.

Significant Difference on the Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH among EPS, Heads and Expert Teachers

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
OBJECTIVES	Between Groups	29.021	1	29.021	4.265*	.045
	Within Groups	285.774	42	6.804		
	Total	314.795	43			
CONTENT	Between Groups	1.706	1	1.706	.271	.605
	Within Groups	264.544	42	6.299		
	Total	266.250	43			
ACTIVITIES	Between Groups	4.994	1	4.994	.798	.377
	Within Groups	262.892	42	6.259		
	Total	267.886	43			
LANGUAGE	Between Groups	1.910	1	1.910	.186	.668
	Within Groups	430.636	42	10.253		
	Total	432.545	43			

The results indicate that there is a significant difference on the description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH among EPS, Heads, and Expert Teachers for the objectives variable ($F=4.265$, $p=.045$). However, there is no significant difference for the CONTENT ($F=.271$, $p=.605$), activities ($F=.798$, $p=.377$), and language ($F=.186$, $p=.668$) variables. It is important to note that the significance level (Sig.) for each variable indicates the probability of obtaining the observed results by chance alone. In this case, a significance level of .05 or lower is typically used to indicate statistical significance, and the OBJECTIVES variable meets this criterion.

Overall, the ANOVA results suggest that there are differences in the way EPS, Heads, and Expert Teachers describe the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH when it comes to objectives, but not for content, activities, and language. Further analysis, such as post-hoc tests, may be needed to identify specific differences between the groups for the objective's variable.

Significant Difference on Student's Description Across Age and Section. The table displays the results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) for two different variables (Section and Age) in relation to the behavior of students.

Table 4.

Significant Difference on the Behavior of Students across Age and Section

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Section	Between Groups	28.346	2	14.173	5.636*	.004
	Within Groups	369.654	147	2.515		
	Total	398.000	149			
Age	Between Groups	8.956	3	2.985	1.120	.343
	Within Groups	389.044	146	2.665		
	Total	398.000	149			

Specifically, the table examines whether there is a significant difference in behavior across different sections (presumably referring to different classes or groups) and different age groups. For each variable, the table shows the Sum of Squares, the degrees of freedom (df), the Mean Square, the F-statistic, and the significance level (Sig.). The results indicate that there is a significant difference in behavior across different sections for the Section variable ($F=5.636$, $p=.004$).

Discussion

Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by Expert Teachers and EPS and Heads. Table 1 displays the average evaluations given to the MAPEH Iconized Exemplar by both Experienced Teachers and EPS and Heads. Mean scores for the various indicators ranged from 4.52 to 4.82, indicating that both groups found the program to be very satisfying. The overall rating of 4.61 on the Composite Mean scale is also very high quality. These results are in line with other studies that have shown the benefits of using an Iconized Exemplar to better understand and

remember new material. The program's success in achieving its goals and proving itself an effective instrument for teaching MAPEH is evidenced by the positive feedback from Expert Teachers, EPSs, and Heads (Lira, 2018). It is worth noting, however, that the mean ratings can only give a rough idea of how content people are with MAPEH's Iconized Exemplar. Expert Teacher, EPS, and Head differences in perception may be better understood with additional study, such as looking at score variability and completing post hoc testing. The verbal adjectives used to describe the mean scores, while helpful, are subjective and may be interpreted differently depending on who you ask. To make these results more objective and trustworthy, further study should investigate different ways of interpreting and reporting mean scores.

Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH as Described by Students. It is essential to keep in mind that the results of this study can only be interpreted verbally, and that the use of a single indicator as well as the subjectivity of the interpretation may restrict the conclusions that can be taken from them. Despite this, the data offers a significant amount of information into the ways in which the students view the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program. In subsequent research, other indicators, more in-depth surveys and interviews, and student perspectives could be used to better investigate student perspectives. In addition, it may be useful to compare the perspectives of students with those of instructors and other stakeholders to discover areas of agreement as well as potential areas for development (Marzan 2018). The research indicates that although there is room for advancement, the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program is judged to be at least satisfactory by students. This is even though there is room for improvement.

Significant Difference in the Description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH among EPS, Heads and Expert Teachers. The findings of the ANOVA analysis on the description of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH by EPS, Heads, and Expert Teachers reveal that there is a significant difference among the groups for the objective's variable. Specifically, the results show that the Expert Teachers and EPS rated the objectives more favorably compared to the Heads. However, there is no significant difference among the groups for the content, activities, and language variables. These results suggest that the Expert Teachers and EPS may have a more aligned perception of the objectives of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH, while the Heads have a different perspective. Further examination through post-hoc tests may be necessary to uncover more detailed differences between the groups (Nunez & Cabacaba, 2020). It is important to note that the findings are limited to the specific indicators and groups studied in this research, and caution should be taken when generalizing the results to other contexts (Reyes & Gomez, 2018).

Significant Difference on Student's Description Across Age and Section. The ANOVA results presented in Table 4 demonstrate that there are significant differences in the behavior of students across different sections. This finding is important as it suggests that factors related to the section or class a student belongs to may be influencing their behavior. However, it is important to note that the ANOVA results cannot provide specific information about which sections are different from each other in terms of behavior. Further analysis, such as post-hoc tests, would be needed to identify specific differences between the sections. In contrast, the ANOVA results did not find a significant difference in behavior across different age groups (Petalcorin & Buenaobra, 2020). This suggests that age may not be a significant factor in influencing behavior among the students in the sample. However, it is important to note that the age variable used in this study may not capture all relevant factors that could influence behavior, and further research may be needed to explore other relevant variables (Palattao, 2019). Overall, the ANOVA results provide important information about the factors that may be influencing the behavior of students in this study, highlighting the potential influence of section but not age.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the data presented in this paper suggests that the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program is a beneficial tool for teaching MAPEH, with high levels of satisfaction reported by Expert Teachers and EPS, as well as positive feedback from students. However, the results also indicate that there are differences in perception among EPS, Heads, and Expert Teachers regarding the objectives of the program, which may need to be further explored. Additionally, the ANOVA results suggest that there are significant differences in behavior across different sections of students, but not across different age groups. These findings highlight the need for further research to understand the factors that influence student behavior and how interventions can be implemented to improve behavior across all sections and age groups. Overall, the results of this study provide important insights into the effectiveness of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program and the factors that may influence student behavior, providing a foundation for further research and improvements in teaching practices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that educators continue to use the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program as a teaching tool. However, it is also important to address the differences in perception among EPS, Heads, and Expert Teachers regarding the objectives of the program. Additional research, such as post-hoc tests, may be necessary to identify specific differences between the groups and to develop strategies that can align the perspectives of all stakeholders. Furthermore, given the significant differences in behavior observed across different sections of students, teachers and school administrators should consider implementing interventions that address these differences and promote positive behavior across all sections. Additional research into the factors that underlie these differences, and the effectiveness of potential interventions is also recommended. By addressing these issues, educators can improve the effectiveness of the Iconized Exemplar in MAPEH program and promote positive behavior among students in all sections and age groups.

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